

CRITERIA OF DEVELOPMENT OF AUTOPEDAGOGIC COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *In this article, the criterion of the development of the teacher's self-pedagogical competence is closely related to the development of an innovative educational environment, it is formed in the process of general pedagogical preparation for professional activity, according to scientists, self-psychological competence is related to the concept of professional self-awareness, self-knowledge and self-development. that it is important in the process of professional formation, the issues of criteria for developing self-pedagogical competence based on professional motives are highlighted.*

Keywords: *self-pedagogical competence, professional activity, professional self-awareness, professional motives, innovative activity, pedagogical skill, creative activity.*

Today, the innovative process in education is the process of improving educational practice, developing educational systems based on innovations, turning an idea into a product, technology, or service. All this requires the innovative teacher to develop and diversify the mechanisms for the development of an innovative educational environment.

The development of an innovative educational environment in an educational institution requires significant changes in the existing pedagogical system, the development of specific educational technologies for each discipline, the creation of a radically new methodological base of educational complexes, and the implementation of new methods and organizational forms of education. Thus, the criterion for the development of the teacher's self-pedagogical competence is closely related to the development of an innovative educational environment, and as its main integrative criterion, it is possible to distinguish the ability to provide all subjects of the educational process with a system of opportunities for effective personal and professional development. The fact that this problem is insufficiently developed at the theoretical and practical level determines the relevance of this research work.

Scientific analyzes show that self-pedagogical competence should be formed in the process of general pedagogical preparation for professional activity.

According to O.A. Abdullina, general pedagogical training of students should be achieved on the basis of ensuring the integrity and systematicity of theoretical and practical education, as well as ensuring their interaction, considering training as a unity of motivational-valuable and meaningful-process aspects, using a system of tools, taking into account specific pedagogical conditions, general pedagogical training of future teachers. The principles of preparation are implemented as the implementation of unity and interrelationship of functions [1; p. 141].

According to N.V. Kuzmina, autopsychological competence is related to the concept of professional self-awareness, self-knowledge and self-development [2]. These terms mean that the teacher has sufficient professional knowledge, ideas about his professional characteristics and knows the technologies for eliminating professional and personal destruction.

The individual-creative approach is one of the methodological foundations of building an innovative activity model. This approach is theoretically based on the works of V.A. Kan-Kalik.

Its essence lies in the fact that it enables the mechanism of general and professional self-development of a person to start and implies motivation and its dynamics in the process of professional formation. The main task of the individual creative approach is to create conditions for self-realization of the individual, diagnosis and development of creative possibilities, the situation of authorship, unique technology of pedagogical activity [3].

Radical changes and updates in the methodology and technology of the organization of the educational process in the institutions of the educational system, pedagogical innovations, innovative direction of the teacher's activity, updating of the educational policy, etc. require the future teacher to be professionally ready for these updates, including self-pedagogical competence.

In order to ensure professional preparation for the innovative changes analyzed above, it is necessary to develop self-pedagogical competence in future teachers.

To analyze and evaluate pedagogical innovations introduced by teachers in the activities of pedagogical teams of educational institutions, managers of methodical services, to create the necessary conditions for their successful development and application, the transition of general education schools to market relations, the creation of a new type, including non-state educational institutions, where their competitiveness creates a real situation is becoming an important trend.

It is known that at the stage of implementation of innovative activities, reflection is accompanied by two processes:

1) the teacher repeatedly returns to the stage of prediction, where he observes the individual constituents of the concept;

2) the second process is related to the reflection on one's activity, that is, the process of goal realization: the analysis of the relationship between the teacher's capabilities and external conditions takes place, innovations, skills, pedagogical actions, content are analyzed.

The processes of the considered teacher's innovative activity determine his actions and behavior. On the basis of innovative behavior lies the ideal and value of excellence realized in the conditions of pedagogical practice. Such behavior is manifested in communication, teaching, self-determination, reflexive processes, etc.

Creativity is an important characteristic in the pedagogical and innovative activity of the teacher. In national psychology, creativity depends on the ability to show socially significant creative activity", creative possibilities of a person, is considered as a specific stable characteristic of a human individual [2].

New requirements for the training of future pedagogues: creation of conditions for preparation for professional activities, related to the rapidly changing content of work and the need for constantly updated knowledge [19; pp. 114-116]. this, in turn, requires the teacher's constant social professional development. This requirement can be fulfilled through self-pedagogical competence.

Because the self-pedagogical competence of the teacher is his inseparable professional and personal characteristic, which determines his readiness and ability to effectively engage in the development of creative potential and self-improvement. Therefore, as a result of the implementation of the idea of self-development in the professional formation of the future teacher, it is possible to achieve a certain level of development of the teacher's self-pedagogical competence system. For this reason, the status of the criteria for the development of professional competence in the preparation of future teachers for professional activities was studied in selected pilot facilities through various pedagogical research methods and the results were determined.

Based on the importance and importance of the self-pedagogical competence discussed above, today the status of the criteria for the development of professional competence in the preparation of future teachers for professional activities was studied and analyzed in pilot facilities. According to his results, despite the wide interest of scientists in the criterion of professional skill and professional skill development of the pedagogue, the problem of the criterion of the development of self-pedagogical competence of the teacher of the future technological education is still not sufficiently studied.

In addition, there is no concept of defining the concept of "Auto-pedagogical competence", differences in its content, professional skills, creativity and self-awareness of the teacher. Thus, to date, the prospects of the criteria for the development of self-pedagogical competence among future teachers in the conditions of the innovative environment of higher education have not been determined, which determined the relevance of this research.

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